

Citizen Science Toolkit for Librarians

<https://www.libocs.ut.ee/toolkit/>

About the Toolkit

The Citizen Science toolkit for Librarians is an open access resource collection created collaboratively by five partners in the Erasmus+ project LibOCS: University Libraries Strengthening the Academia-Society Connection through Citizen Science in the Baltics.

The toolkit is available from following link:

<https://www.libocs.ut.ee/toolkit/>

Information

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Origin of pictures: Unsplash.

In case of errors, please let us know.

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